

Si–H Bond Activation with Bullock’s Cationic Tungsten(II) Catalyst: CO as Cooperating Ligand

Julien Fuchs,[†] Elisabeth Irran,[†] Peter Hrobárik,^{*,‡} Hendrik F. T. Klare,^{*,†} and Martin Oestreich^{*,†}

[†]Institut für Chemie, Technische Universität Berlin, Strasse des 17. Juni 115, 10623 Berlin, Germany

[‡]Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Comenius University, 84215 Bratislava, Slovakia

ABSTRACT: An in-depth investigation of the reaction of tertiary hydrosilanes with $[\text{CpW}(\text{CO})_2(\text{IMes})]^+[\text{B}(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_4]^-$ reveals a fundamentally new Si–H bond activation mode. Unlike the originally proposed oxidative addition of the Si–H bond to the tungsten(II) center, there is strong experimental and NMR spectroscopic evidence for the involvement of one of the CO ligands of the cationic complex in the Si–H bond breaking event. The Si–H bond is heterolytically cleaved to form a tungsten(II) hydride and a silylium ion, which is stabilized by one of the CO ligands. This reactive hydrosilane adduct was eventually isolated and characterized by X-ray diffraction analysis. Quantum-chemical calculations support a cooperative mechanism but a stepwise process consisting of oxidative addition and subsequent tungsten-to-oxygen silyl migration in the tungsten(IV) silyl hydride is also energetically feasible. However, our combined spectroscopic and computational analysis favors the cooperative pathway. The newly identified hydrosilane adduct is the key intermediate of Bullock’s ionic carbonyl hydrosilylation.

INTRODUCTION

The activation of hydrosilanes by transition-metal complexes spans a wide range of bonding scenarios¹ leading to different mechanisms for carbonyl hydrosilylation.^{2,3} Oxidative addition of the hydrosilane to the metal center (**I** + **II** → **III**) is commonly seen with neutral electron-rich transition metals. This redox process is the initial step of the classic Ojima-type mechanism⁴ (Scheme 1, right cycle) and is followed by migratory insertion of the coordinated carbonyl compound into the M–Si bond (**III** + **IV** → **V**). Reductive elimination releases the silyl ether and closes the catalytic cycle (**V** → **VI** + **I**). Conversely, nonclassical σ interactions of hydrosilanes with a metal center as in η^1 - or η^2 -complexes are usually observed when using electrophilic cationic transition metals (**VII** + **II** → **VIII**),⁵ resulting in ionic outer-sphere hydrosilylations (Scheme 1, left cycle).³ Here, silyl transfer to the carbonyl oxygen atom (**VIII** + **IV** → **IX** + **X**) and subsequent transfer of the hydride to the silylcarboxonium ion (**IX** + **X** → **VI** + **VII**) are the key bond-forming events, and the metal does not change its oxidation state.

Scheme 1. Transition-Metal Catalyzed Carbonyl Hydrosilylation: Ojima-Type (Right) and Ionic Outer-Sphere Mechanism (Left)^a

^aSi = triorganosilyl (R₃Si).

In 2003, Bullock and co-workers introduced a recyclable cationic tungsten(II) catalyst⁶ **1**⁺ for carbonyl hydrosilylation.⁷ Rather atypical for cationic transition-metal complexes, an oxidative addition of hydrosilane **2** to complex **1**⁺ was postulated to form tungsten(IV) silyl hydride **3**⁺ (Scheme 2). This step is typically the entry into an Ojima-type catalytic cycle but Bullock’s proposal switches to an ionic outer-sphere mechanism where silyl transfer from **3**⁺ to the carbonyl oxygen atom of **4** is followed by hydride transfer from the neutral monohydride **5** to silylcarboxonium ion **6**⁺ to yield silyl ether **7**.⁸ This unique proposal prompted us to look into the hydrosilylation of acetophenone (**4**) using Bullock’s complex **1**⁺.

Scheme 2. Proposed Catalytic Cycle for the Carbonyl Hydrosilylation with Bullock’s Complex

^aThe $[\text{B}(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_4]^-$ counteranion is omitted for clarity. IMes = 1,3-dimesitylimidazol-2-ylidene, Mes = 2,4,6-trimethylphenyl.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As the oxidative addition of hydrosilane **2** to complex **1**⁺ was not secure, we began with an investigation of the hydrosilane-activation step. An equimolar mixture of Et₃SiH (**2a**) and **1**⁺ in deuterated chlorobenzene was submitted to NMR spectroscopic analysis, revealing the clean formation of a tungsten(II) hydride featuring a hydride shift of $\delta = -2.52$ ppm with the corresponding tungsten satellites (¹J_{W,H} = 36 Hz) in the ¹H NMR spectrum (Figure 1, left). Further characterization of this compound disclosed two notable facts: (1) The ¹³C NMR chemical shifts for the two CO ligands at δ 216.6 and 240.6 ppm were significantly different, in contrast to those seen for complex **1**⁺ at δ 247.1 and 246.2 ppm.⁹ (2) The resonance signal in the ²⁹Si NMR spectrum at δ 42.7 ppm showed no tungsten satellites, indicating that the silyl group might not be attached to the tungsten center (Figure 1, right). However, we were not able to conclusively assign the structure of **8a**⁺ solely based on NMR spectroscopic measurements.

Figure 1. Selected segments of the ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, C₆D₅Cl, 300 K) (left) and ²⁹Si NMR spectrum (99 MHz, C₆D₅Cl, 300 K) (right) of hydrosilane adduct **8a**⁺[B(C₆F₅)₄]⁻.

The successful crystallization of hydrosilane adduct **8a**⁺ from neat hydrosilane **2a** and X-ray diffraction analysis then revealed its molecular structure (Scheme 3).¹⁰ The formation of **8a**⁺ is the result of heterolytic cleavage of the Si–H bond by complex **1**⁺. A silylium ion stabilized by a carbonyl oxygen atom is in accordance with the observed downfield shift of the resonance in the ²⁹Si NMR spectrum.¹¹ This result is, to the best of our knowledge, the first example of a heterolytic Si–H bond activation by a cationic transition metal complex with participation of a CO ligand.^{12–14} The C–O bond of the silylated CO ligand [1.25 Å] in the solid-state structure of **8a**⁺ is substantially longer than the C–O bond reported for neutral tungsten(II) monohydride **5** [1.17 Å]⁶ (without the silyl group). In contrast, the W–C_{OSi} bond in **8a**⁺ [1.79 Å] is significantly shorter than the corresponding W–C_{CO} bond in **5** [1.94 Å] and close to the sum of the triple-bond covalent radii [1.75 Å],¹⁵ thus featuring a carbyne-like character (W≡C–OSi) as also evident from the natural localized molecular orbital (NLMO) analysis (cf. Figures S18 and S19 in the Supporting Information). The W–H bond in **8a**⁺ [1.73 Å] is similar to the W–H bond in **5** [1.78 Å]. The average O–Si–C angle in **8a**⁺ [103.7°] as well as the O–Si bond length [1.80 Å] are comparable to the reported values of the benzaldehyde-stabilized silylium ion [C₆H₅CHO·SiEt₃]⁺[CHB₁₁H₅Br₆]⁻ [104.25° and 1.78 Å].¹⁶ The sum of all C–Si–C angles of 345.8° in **8a**⁺ is larger than the reported value for [C₆H₅CHO·SiEt₃]⁺[CHB₁₁H₅Br₆]⁻ [342.5°], consistent with a highly electrophilic silicon atom having a distorted trigonal spatial arrangement of the substituents. This is also reflected by a natural population analysis (NPA), showing that the positive charge is mainly located at the silicon atom in **8a**⁺ (cf. Figure S17 in the Supporting Information).

Scheme 3. Synthesis and Molecular Structure of Hydrosilane Adduct **8a**⁺[B(C₆F₅)₄]⁻

^aThermal ellipsoids are shown at the 50% probability level; counteranion and hydrogen atoms except for W–H are omitted for clarity. Selected interatomic distances (Å) and angles (deg): W–H: 1.73, W–C_{CO}: 1.98, O–C_{CO}: 1.16, W–C_{OSi}: 1.79, O–C_{OSi}: 1.25, O–Si: 1.80, Si–O–C_{CO}: 124.2°, av(O–Si–C): 103.7°, Σ (C–Si–C): 345.8°.¹⁰

Notably, the solid-state structure of hydrosilane adduct **8a**⁺ features *cis* configuration of the CO groups, while the NMR chemical shifts of **8a**⁺ in solution better match the *trans* isomer, which was computed to be 0.4 kcal mol⁻¹ energetically less stable (cf. Table S3 in the Supporting Information). Its preference in solution could be attributed to a counteranion effect and/or specific solvent-solute interactions not considered in the implicit solvent model. Dissolving crystals of hydrosilane adduct *cis*-**8a**⁺ in deuterated chlorobenzene immediately resulted in isomerization to the *trans* isomer. DFT calculations confirmed that the *cis*-*trans* isomerization is a facile process, proceeding quickly at room temperature through transition state **TS-8a**⁺ over a low barrier of 9.5 kcal mol⁻¹ (Scheme 4 and Figure S16 in the Supporting Information).

Scheme 4. Calculated relative free energies (ΔG_r^0 , in kcal mol⁻¹) for the *cis*-*trans* isomerization of hydrosilane adduct **8a**⁺^a

^aResults obtained at the B3LYP-D3(BJ)/ECP/6-31+G** level of theory using an SMD solvation model.

To gain deeper insight into the hydrosilane activation step, we employed quantum-chemical calculations (Figure 2). The relativistic DFT calculations revealed that neither tungsten(IV) silyl hydride **3a**⁺ formed by oxidative addition of Et₃SiH (**2a**) nor η^1 -complex **9a**⁺ with end-on coordination of the hydrosilane, both previously considered as the active species,^{7,8} match the experimental fingerprint resonances given above. Instead, a very good agreement for the key ¹H, ¹³C, and ²⁹Si NMR signals was found for the structure of hydrosilane adduct *trans*-**8a**⁺ (cf. Table S3 in the Supporting Information). According to the quantum-chemical calculations, **8a**⁺ represents the energetic minimum among possible adducts of Bullock's tungsten(II) complex **1**⁺ with hydrosilane **2a**, whereas the corresponding η^1 -complex **9a**⁺ and tungsten(IV) silyl hydride **3a**⁺ are higher in energy by 3.3 and 11.8 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. Coordination of the hydrosilane to the electrophilic unsaturated 16-valence-electron complex **1**⁺ proceeds barrierless and is exergonic by 9.0 kcal mol⁻¹ (blue pathway). The barrier of 29.3 kcal mol⁻¹ for the subsequent heterolytic Si–H bond cleavage through transition state **8a**⁺_TS-A is too high in view of the fact that the formation of **8a**⁺ is a fast reaction at room temperature. However, the barrier for a concerted ligand-assisted process through the same transition state would be 20.3 kcal mol⁻¹ and thus a conceivable pathway (dashed green pathway). This activation energy is almost twice as high as in the cooperative Si–H bond activation

by cationic ruthenium(II) thiolate complexes,¹⁷ but still corresponds to a reaction half-time of about one to two minutes at room temperature according to the Arrhenius equation. In contrast, the reaction barrier for the backward reaction is too high (> 30 kcal mol⁻¹), explaining the irreversibility of the hydrosilane activation process (see below). An alternative mechanism for the formation of adduct **8a**⁺ could involve formation of silyl hydride **3a**⁺ through oxidative addition of Et₃SiH (**2a**) to complex **1**⁺ followed by a 1,3-silyl shift from tungsten to the oxygen atom of one of the bound carbonyl ligand (red pathway). Such a sequence was also proposed for the formation of siloxycarbyne complexes from *neutral* transition metal carbonyl complexes.¹⁸ The computed barriers of 5.9 kcal mol⁻¹ for oxidative addition through transition state **3a**⁺_TS and 19.5 kcal mol⁻¹ for silyl migration through transition state **8a**⁺_TS-B indeed suggest that this route is energetically possible. To distinguish between both mechanistic scenarios, we performed low-temperature NMR measurements. The Si–H bond heterolysis by complex **1**⁺ also occurs at –40 °C in deuterated chlorobenzene, yet requiring longer reaction time (> 1 h) until complete conversion of hydrosilane **2a**. However, no intermediates and no other hydrides than **8a**⁺ were detected, suggesting that a concerted cooperative Si–H bond activation mode through transition state **8a**⁺_TS-A is operative (dashed green pathway). However, the oxidative addition–silyl migration pathway cannot be completely ruled out at this stage.

Figure 2. Calculated reaction free energies (ΔG^0 , in kcal mol⁻¹) for three different pathways of Si–H bond activation of Et₃SiH (**2a**) by cationic complex **1**⁺. Results obtained at the B3LYP-D3(BJ)/ECP/6-31+G** level of theory using an SMD solvation model.

To explore the reactivity and role of hydrosilane adduct $8a^+$ in the hydrosilylation, we conducted catalytic and stoichiometric control experiments. To probe its ability to act as precatalyst in the hydrosilylation reaction, we added catalytic amounts of $8a^+$ to an almost equimolar mixture of hydrosilane **2a** and ketone **4** (Scheme 4). Full conversion to silyl ether **7a** was observed.

Scheme 4. Catalytic Activity of Hydrosilane Adduct $8a^+$

We were also interested to experimentally verify whether the activation of the hydrosilane is reversible or not. Consistent with the computations (see above), a NOESY NMR measurement showed no chemical exchange between hydrosilane adduct $8a^+$ and free hydrosilane **2a**. However, mixing adduct $8b^+$ and deuterated hydrosilane Et_3SiD (**2a-d₁**) in a crossover experiment revealed exchange of the silyl group at the CO ligand in $8b^+$ along with formation of Me_2PhSiD (**2b-d₁**) (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5. Probing the Reversibility of the Hydrosilane Activation by a Stoichiometric Crossover Experiment

^aRatios determined by NMR spectroscopic analysis.

Surprisingly, the expected tungsten(II) deuteride $8^+ - d_1$ was not detected in the ²H NMR spectrum, implying that the exchange of the silyl group proceeds without participation of the hydride at the tungsten center. Two mechanistic pictures can explain these results. Pathway A involves a σ -bond metathesis at the CO ligand through **TS-I**,¹⁹ while pathway B proceeds by an S_N2 -type silyl transfer to deuterated hydrosilane **2a-d₁** under formation of hydronium ion **10⁺** and neutral tungsten(II) monohydride **5** through **TS-II** (Scheme 6, top).²⁰ To distinguish between these pathways, silicon-stereogenic hydrosilane (^{Si}S)-**2c**²¹ with an enantiomeric ratio (e.r.) = 90:10 was employed as a stereochemical probe (Scheme 6, bottom). Mixing enantioenriched (^{Si}S)-**2c** with catalytic amounts of tungsten(II) complex **1⁺** does not cause any loss of enantiomeric purity. This retention of the configuration at the silicon atom suggests a σ -bond metathesis (**TS-I**) as an S_N2 -type silyl transfer (**TS-II**) would lead to (at least) partial racemization at the silicon atom.¹⁷

Scheme 6. Probing Mechanistic Pathways for the Silyl Group Exchange

CONCLUSION

Based on our experimental findings and computations we suggest a revised catalytic cycle for the ionic outer-sphere hydrosilylation with tungsten(II) complex **1⁺** (Scheme 7). The initial step is the irreversible activation of the Si-H bond in hydrosilane **2** by **1⁺** with involvement of one of the CO ligands. The resulting electrophilic silicon compound 8^+ transfers its silyl group S_N2 -like to the carbonyl oxygen atom of acetophenone (**4**) in a reversible, energetically downhill reaction. Additionally, 8^+ can undergo a silyl group exchange at the CO ligand with hydrosilane **2** by a σ -bond metathesis (**TS-I**). The silylcarboxonium ion **6⁺** can alternatively form pentacoordinate silicon compound **11⁺** with another molecule of acetophenone (**4**). This explains racemization at the silicon atom using silicon-stereogenic hydrosilane (^{Si}S)-**2c** for the hydrosilylation of **4** (not shown; see the Supporting Information for details). Monohydride **5** is able to undergo hydride transfer to the silylcarboxonium ion **6⁺** but needs the assistance of another hydrosilane molecule **2** to release silyl ether **7** with regeneration of adduct 8^+ .²²

Scheme 7. Revised Catalytic Cycle for the Ionic Outer-Sphere Hydrosilylation with Bullock's Complex

In summary, we were able to confirm an ionic outer-sphere mechanism for the hydrosilylation with Bullock's cationic tungsten(II) catalyst. Strikingly, the CO ligand is cooperating in this catalysis and engages in the Si–H bond activation event, leading to the formation of a stable carbonyl-oxygen-stabilized silylium ion and a tungsten(II) hydride. In accordance with our earlier studies,²³ this analysis confirms that Bullock's catalyst is now the third example for a cationic transition-metal complex to follow a two-silicon cycle in a carbonyl hydrosilylation.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

Experimental details, spectroscopic, crystallographic and computational data (PDF)

X-ray crystallographic data (CIF)

Cartesian coordinates of the selected DFT optimized structures (XYZ)

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

peter.hrobarik@uniba.sk;
hendrik.klare@tu-berlin.de;
martin.oestreich@tu-berlin.de

ORCID

Julien Fuchs: 0000-0003-0816-6497
Elisabeth Irran: 0000-0001-6098-1996
Peter Hrobárik: 0000-0002-6444-8555
Hendrik F. T. Klare: 0000-0003-3748-6609
Martin Oestreich: 0000-0002-1487-9218

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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- (10) Due to disorder in the crystal, another structure of hydrosilane adduct *cis*- $\mathbf{8a}^+$ with different interatomic distances and angles for the silylated CO ligand was found. In Scheme 3, duplicated atoms are omitted for clarity. Selected interatomic distances (Å) and angles (deg) for the second version: W–H: 1.73, W–Cco: 1.98, O–Cco: 1.16, W–Ccosi: 1.79, O–Ccosi: 1.36, O–Si: 1.74, Si–O–Cco: 136.5°, $\text{av}(\text{O–Si–C})$: 104.1°, $\Sigma(\text{C–Si–C})$: 343°.
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CO as cooperating ligand

